

TENSILE FATIGUE PERFORMANCE OF THERMOPLASTIC RESIN COMPOSITES
REINFORCED WITH ORDERED KEVLAR* ARAMID STAPLE

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ABSTRACT

Unidirectional composites reinforced with ordered staple having lengths of 1 to 4 inch have been subjected to load controlled cyclic tensile fatigue and have been found to have overall performance essentially equivalent to continuous fiber reinforced composites. This work mainly focuses on J-2 thermoplastic matrix reinforced with "Kevlar" aramid fibers; other systems using other matrices and/or other fibers are expected to perform similarly. Differences in fracture appearance and failure history between the continuous and ordered staple composite systems will be discussed.

INTRODUCTION

The advent of thermoplastics as matrices for high performance composites has presented opportunities of thermoforming parts from flat laminated composite sheets; a process envisioned akin to metal stamping albeit at elevated temperatures. However, the reinforcing fiber only has strain-to-failure of 1-3%, thus limiting the stretching process. Therefore, methods to form the parts without stretching the fiber beyond its limits are necessary. Composites based on drapable woven fiber reinforcements such as satin weaves do offer possibility such that the fiber can conform to the shape during the forming process. Despite the formability merits of fabrics, their use entails some penalties in initial properties as compared to continuous fiber prepreg laminated construction and to some extent constrains the fiber reinforcement direction. An alternative to the fabric approach is to have a reinforcement that will stretch beyond its strain limits but still maintain a respectable modicum of continuous fiber properties. Such a reinforcement has been introduced by E. I. du Pont de Nemours & Co., Inc. in the use of ordered staple where the staple lengths are 1-4 inch and hence are in a category apart from short fiber reinforcement.

This reinforcement concept was developed by a team of researchers and their work was presented in a paper by Okine, Edison and Little.¹ They were able to come up with a system in which >85% of the long staple fibers (1-6 inch) were aligned to within $\pm 5^\circ$ in a thermoplastic matrix. Based on such a system they claimed 90% of the mechanical properties of continuous reinforced composites and showed an impressive example of hemispherical forming of the system with quasi-isotropic layup. Later Medwin² demonstrated the forming of a helicopter seat from the same system.

The introduction of any new material or variation on existing materials and techniques requires the accumulation of property data for confident design application.

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Although Reference 1 gave some basic mechanical data for ordered staple reinforced composites, the amount of data was only initial and hence not complete. This was especially true for dynamic properties such as fatigue. The purpose of this work is to supply some fatigue data and to examine performance differences between ordered staple and continuous fiber reinforced composites. The differences in fatigue failure as well as life and strength differences will also be addressed. Test samples for this work used "Kevlar" aramid fiber as the composite reinforcement and J-2 as the polymeric matrix. J-2 is an amorphous resin of the broad polyamide class based on bis (para-amino cyclohexyl) methane.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

Unidirectional laminated composites of J-2 thermoplastic matrix reinforced with "Kevlar" aramid fiber were made using heat and pressure. The ordered staple based composite preparation has been detailed in Reference 1. The continuous fiber based composite preparation has been detailed in References 3 and 4. Tensile longitudinal specimens were cut from the laminated panels and had widths of 1/2 inch. The sample thickness varied from 30 to 60 mils and the lengths from 9 to 12 inches. The samples were tabbed with 1-1/2 inch long aluminum tabs (a few samples were tabbed with fiber-glass tabs but no difference in test results were observed). Therefore, the distance between tabs was at least 6 inches. The fiber volume loading for the continuous fiber system was ~60%; the loading for the ordered staple system was ~50%.

TEST PROCEDURE

For baseline data several samples were tested for static tensile properties using an Instron screw driven tensile tester equipped with wedge action grips. The crosshead test rate was 0.05 inch/minute and testing was performed to complete specimen failure. On selected samples longitudinal and transverse strains were monitored by 350 Ω bidirectional strain gages of the CEA-06-125UT-350 type (Micromasurements Group).

Fatigue testing was performed on an MTS servo hydraulic test machine equipped with hydraulic grips. Testing was performed under load control (sinusoidal loading) in tension with an R ratio of 0.1. Testing frequency was maintained at 5 Hz to prevent specimen heat up. For the most part the cycles-to-failure were recorded with visual observations of damage noted for some of the specimens. Failure was defined as complete breakage of the specimen such that application of the test load was no longer possible. Some load-extension hysteresis monitoring was performed on the continuous fiber reinforced specimens.

Both static and fatigue testing were performed at room temperature. Static testing was performed under controlled humidity conditions, fatigue testing was not. The loadings were applied in the fiber direction of the longitudinal specimens.

RESULTS

1. Static

Table 1 compares the moduli, ultimate stress, strain-to-failure, and Poisson's ratio of the continuous fiber and ordered staple reinforced J-2 polymer systems. Data for epoxy reinforced with "Kevlar" aramid fiber is provided also for comparison. The stress-strain curves for both the J-2 polymer reinforced with continuous and ordered staple fiber have upward curvatures.

Table 1 Static performance of unidirectional composites reinforced with Kevlar* aramid fiber

Fiber Form	% v/o	Modulus Mpsi	Strength kpsi	Strain %	Poisson's Ratio
a. J-2 Matrix					
Continuous	60	11	180	1.6	0.36
Ordered Staple	50	8	140	1.7	0.4
b. Epoxy					
Continuous	>60	12	220	1.8	0.39

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2. Fatigue

Fig. 1 gives the life in cycles for specimens subjected to a maximum fatigue load for the continuous and ordered staple systems. The static data is plotted along the vertical axis at 1 cycle. An arrow on a data point indicates that the specimen did not fail but the test was stopped because of time restraints (1 million cycles @ 5 Hz = 55 hours), machine malfunction, residual strength measurement, etc.). The ordered staple data has been normalized to 60% v/o.

Fig. 1: Tension-Tension Fatigue, all Data Normalized to 60% Fiber v/o

DISCUSSION

1. Static Data

The range in static test data is evident in Fig. 1. Despite the disparity in the number of data points between the continuous fiber and ordered staple fiber systems, it is apparent that the ordered staple system shows less scatter in static strength. The range of static strength data for the ordered staple system extends from 160 kpsi to 175 kpsi; the range in static strength data for the continuous system extends from 140 kpsi to 200 kpsi. The average ordered staple composite strength is 168 kpsi, the average continuous fiber composite strength is 180 kpsi. Therefore, the ordered staple system gives a strength of >90% of the continuous fiber system strength with considerably less data scatter.

There are several precedents in the literature to suggest and reinforce the observations made here. Mills, Brown and Waterman⁵ looked at pre-stressing the composite prepreg before composite lamination. This resulted in improved "B" design allowable levels for boron and graphite-epoxy composites because the weak fibers were broken in the prepreg stressing operation. Bell⁶ looked at the application of preload on the graphite/epoxy composite tow prior to fabrication of the laminate and showed that by breaking the weak fibers, the shape of the Weibull distribution describing the composite strength data could be changed with an increase in composite reliability. For instance, he found the standard deviation in strength data improved by 31% while the mean strength dropped by only 1% for a set of samples made from preloaded fiber bundles vs. those made by more conventional techniques.

Basically the strength data observed here plus the work reported in References 5 and 6 suggest the composite strength distribution can be narrowed by eliminating the weak fibers. One way to do that is to break the weak fibers so that they do not break in the composite and cause premature failure by their associated energy release and stress intensification and sudden demand upon neighboring fibers to take up the load. On the other hand, the data in Fig. 1 does suggest that the extreme high values for the continuous fiber system are not seen in the ordered staple system composites. However, design should be more concerned with the lower values of the performance distribution than the higher values; hence one can argue that the ordered staple system is the more reliable system.

2. Fatigue Data

Fig. 1 also shows the comparison between the tension-tension fatigue performance of the ordered-staple and continuous fiber reinforced composites. A first way to describe the fatigue performance is to establish an endurance limit. Arbitrarily the endurance limit is defined here as that maximum value of fatigue load that gives a reasonable expectation of 1 million fatigue cycle survival. Fig. 1 then suggests that the endurance limit for both systems is ~90 kpsi.

In general, the continuous fiber composite system sustains somewhat higher fatigue loads than the ordered staple system. However, as the fatigue load is lowered, both systems show similar survival. Interestingly, the scatter in life data at a given load appears to be less for the continuous fiber system than for the ordered fiber system. However, for both systems the scatter seems to decrease as the fatigue load is lowered.

3. Failure History and Fracture

A. Static

The continuous fiber and the ordered staple reinforced J-2 matrix specimens subjected to static loading give little if any warning of impending failure. The failures of both systems, are catastrophic and representative fractures are shown in Fig. 2. The continuous fiber specimen failures looks more splintery or stringy than the ordered staple specimen and the ordered staple specimen shows more grouping of fiber breaks. The failure appearance of the ordered staple system is probably due to the fact that only the strongest segments of the fiber fail upon testing of the composite since the weaker segments have been broken prior to fabrication of the sample. The failure of the strongest fiber, however, results in a large release of ener-

Fig. 2: Static Failure of Composite with Kevlar* Fiber Reinforcement
Left: Ordered Staple
Right: Continuous

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which may quickly propagate failure to the surrounding region causing a more catastrophic looking fracture. On the other hand the continuous fiber system will have failures in the weak fiber segments long before final failure, however, these weak fiber failures most probably are not visually observable. It would be interesting to compare the acoustic emission response of both systems to static testing.

B. Fatigue

In general, specimens of both the ordered staple and continuous fiber system subjected to tension-tension fatigue show failures that look similar to those seen in Fig. 2. In short, under casual examination, a statically failed specimen looks the same as a fatigue failed specimen. However, the fatigued sample shows damage long before final specimen failure. The continuous fiber specimen shows vertical cracks, i.e., cracks parallel to the fiber and to the loading direction, many cycles prior to failure. For instance, a specimen fatigued at 120 kpsi maximum load showed some damage at 88,000 cycles; a steep angled vertical crack from top to bottom at 461,000 cycles and final failure at 560,000 cycles. The ordered staple sample also shows damage many cycles prior to final fatigue failure. The initial damage appears as minute capital H's. The cross piece of the "H" is believed to be an array of broken fibers rising up on the surface. The verticals of the "H" are cracks parallel to the fiber and loading directions. The "H's" increase in number and severity as fatigue proceeds. It is conceivable that the verticals will propagate and intersect other "H" damage regions, thus weakening the sample and causing final fatigue failure. As an example, an ordered staple sample fatigued at 130 kpsi maximum load showed several "H" damage marks at 37,000 cycles, but did not fail until 81,800 cycles.

Fig. 3 shows a photo of one of the "H" damage marks on a fatigue failed ordered staple sample. The "H" is $\sim 1/16$ " wide and $\sim 3/8$ " long. As can be seen the surface of the specimen is slightly raised in the vicinity of the horizontal portion of the damage and there are small vertical cracks in this area. The specimen was sectioned parallel to the horizontal damage to access the damage depth and these showed fiber matrix cracking, delaminations and fiber failures to $\sim 1/4$ the thickness of the specimen. The vertical crack just to the left of the "H" extended the full thickness of the specimen.

These descriptions of the observed events for the fatigue failure history point out that more is happening than just fiber failure. Although ultimate failure is governed by fiber failure, the other observed events must play a role in the timing of ultimate failure and the statistics of these failures.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the static and fatigue data presented here and the observed failure and fracture behaviors reported, the following conclusions can be proposed.

- The J-2 matrix system reinforced with ordered staple "Kevlar" has better than 90% of the unidirectional strength of the continuous fiber reinforced system. The ordered staple system has less scatter in the static strength data than the continuous fiber system and this is probably due to breaking of the weak fiber elements inherent with the ordered staple system prior to sample preparation.
- Both the ordered staple system and the continuous fiber system appear to have similar fatigue endurance behavior with a defined endurance limit at ~ 90 kpsi.

Fig. 3: Surface Damage of Ordered Staple Reinforced J-2 Matrix Composite Subjected To Fatigue

The fatigue failure of both the ordered staple system and the continuous fiber system show visible damage many cycles before ultimate failure. The ordered staple system shows initial fatigue damage as minute "H's". The continuous fiber system shows initial fatigue damage by cracking parallel to the fiber and the loading direction.

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